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Association Between Cyberbullying Behaviour And Student's Emotional Health And Well-Being In Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study examined emotional well-being and cyber bullying of adolescent's secondary school students in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study is 28, 634 students in public secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. Multi stage sampling procedure, Simple random sampling technique and purposive random sampling technique was used to sample 450 male and female SSS 2 adolescents. Data was collected using Emotional well-being survey (EWB) and Cyber bullying questionnaire (CBQ) by Prins, Bovin, Kimerling, Kaloupex, Marx, Kaiser & Schnurr (2015). Cronbach alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the instruments, Cyber bullying has $r = .75$, Emotional well-being has $r = .69$ after pilot testing. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive (mean and standard deviation), PPMC and Independent T-test statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings show that there is a positive relationship between emotional well-being and cyber bullying of adolescents' secondary school students ($r = .459$, $p = .000$). Gender and emotional well-being of secondary school adolescent students ($r = .500$, $p = .000$). Therefore, it was recommended among others, that traumatized adolescents should be empowered to improved their social skills and competence to prevent cyber bullying and emotional health problems. Government and school owners should provide counselling centers in every school for counselling adolescents with psychological problems.

Keywords: Cyber bullying, Emotional well-being, Gender, Adolescents.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of cyber bullying is becoming worrisome globally as adolescents at secondary school level are engaging in it as a platform for assaulting and causing mental harm to their peers at school and outside the school premises. The use of social media for communication and interaction alongside its use for video chatting has brought about its manipulative use for cyber bullying that has brought about emotional health consequences that leads to depression, anxiety, headaches and suicidal ideation. The negative

consequences of cyber bullying in the short, medium, and long term have been widely acknowledged (Kowalski et al., 2014; Schoeler et al., 2018; Young-Jones et al., 2015), highlighting that both bullies and victim students are at a greater risk of suffering emotional maladjustment and psychopathological disorders and symptoms in adolescence and adult life. Furthermore, some authors have pointed out that the effects of cyber bullying can be more devastating than those of traditional bullying, especially among victimized students (Baier et al., 2019).

Adolescents in the several cultures are moving from using the Internet as an “extra” in everyday communication (cyber utilization) to using it as a “primary and necessary” mode of communication (cyber immersion). In fact, 95% of adolescents are connected to the Internet (Englander, 2022). This shift from face-to-face communication to online communication has created a unique and potentially harmful dynamic for social relationships. In general, cyber bullying involves hurting someone else using information and communication technologies. This may include sending harassing messages (via text or Internet), posting disparaging comments on a social networking site, posting humiliating pictures, or threatening/intimidating someone electronically (Kowalski & Limber, 2017).

Sadly, cyberbullying has become a normalized and even expected part of life for many adolescents today. Unlike traditional bullying, cyberbullying stands out because it can reach an almost limitless audience and remains accessible over time and across different platforms. The messages, images, and videos shared online often stay there indefinitely, creating lasting impacts. What makes it even more troubling is that it usually happens without adult supervision. Because those who engage in cyberbullying don't see the emotional reactions of their victims face-to-face (Hinduja & Patchin, 2019), they may struggle to fully grasp the harm they're causing. This emotional distance can reduce their sense of personal responsibility, a phenomenon researcher has described as the “disinhibition effect” (Patchin & Hinduja, 2016). Cyber bullying has emerged as a relatively new form of bullying within the last decade (Hinduja & Patchin, 2018; Smith, Barrio & Tokunaga, 2013). This new focus on cyber bullying has, in part, been driven by recent news media highlighting the connection between cyber bullying and adolescent suicides and health outcome especially mental health (USAToday, 2013), with one of the most recent cases involving Rebecca Sedwick, a 12-year-old girl from Polk County, Florida, USA who jumped to her death after experiencing relentless acts of cyber bullying. Initial work on cyber bullying has focused on documenting prevalence rates, sex-related effects, and identifying similarities/differences to traditional forms of bullying. More recently, work has been conducted on establishing the psychosocial (for example, depression, and anxiety) and psychosomatic correlates (for example, headaches, and stomachaches) of cyber bullying.

Given that cyber bullying is a relatively new construct, it is important to note that there are still definitional and methodological inconsistencies throughout the literature. For example, some scholars have chosen to adopt a more conservative criterion to define cyber bullying (for example, “willful and repeated harm inflicted through the use of computers, cell phones, and other electronic devices (Ybarra & Mitchell, 2017), while other scholars have used a more broad definition (for example, “using electronic means to intentionally harm someone else (Campbell, Spears, Slee, Butler & Kift, 2012). The term cyber bullying in this study represent an umbrella term that includes related constructs such as Internet bullying, online bullying, and information communication technologies and Internet harassment. Another inconsistency in the literature includes the use of different reference points when assessing adolescents' involvement with cyber bullying (Juvonen & Gross, 2018). On a more definitive term, cyber bullying is a combination of two words, cyber and bullying. Bullying is defined as aggressive behaviour that is intentionally and repeatedly directed at an individual who holds less power than the aggressor (Olweus, 2013). Bullying takes many forms, including physical (e.g., hitting, shoving, spitting), verbal (e.g., taunting, name calling, threatening), and social (e.g., rumour spreading, peer group exclusion). Cyber bullying is an intentional, repeated act of harm toward others through electronic tools (Krešić Ćorić & Kaštelan, 2020). With the surge in information and data sharing in the emerging digital world, a new era of socialization through digital tools, and the popularization of social media, cyber bullying has become

more frequent than ever and occurs when there is inadequate adult supervision (Martín-Criado, Casas & Ortega-Ruiz, 2021; Uludasdemir & Kucuk, 2019).

A large study that looked at the incidence of cyber bullying among adolescents in England found a prevalence of 17.9%, while one study conducted in Saudi Arabia found a prevalence of 20.97% (Jaffer et al., 2021). Cyber bullying can take many forms, including sending angry, rude, or offensive messages; intimidating, cruel, and possibly false information about a person to others; sharing sensitive or private information (outing); and exclusion, which involves purposefully leaving someone out of an online group. Cyber bullying can be influenced by age, gender, parent-child relationships, and time spent on the Internet (social media) (Rao, Wan & Pang, 2019; Samples-Kanyinga, Lalande & Colman, 2018). Although some studies have found that cyber bullying continues to increase in late adolescence, others found that cyber bullying tends to peak at 14 and 15 years old before decreasing through the remaining years of adolescence (Pichel, Foody, O'Higgins Norman, Feijóo, Varela, & Rial, 2021).

Unlike traditional Bullying, which usually only occurs in school and is mitigated at home, victims of cyber bullying can be contacted anytime and anywhere. Parents and teachers are seen as saviors in cases of traditional Bullying. Simultaneously, in cyber bullying, children tend to be reluctant to tell adults for fear of losing access to their phones and computers, so they would in most cases, hide the cyber bullying incident (Cassidy, Jackson & Brown, 2019). Reports show that cyber bullying is a form of harm not easily avoided by the victim. In addition, in the cyber form of Bullying, identification of the victim and the perpetrator is generally challenging compared to traditional Bullying, this makes an accurate estimation of the problem widely contested (Bonanno & Hyme, 2013; Peebles, 2014).

There is increasing evidence that cyberbullying has a more profound emotional impact on adolescents than traditional forms of bullying. It tends to leave deeper scars, often leading to heightened levels of depression, anxiety, and loneliness. Several comprehensive studies have highlighted the troubling connection between both experiencing and engaging in bullying—especially online—and serious mental health issues like suicidal thoughts and depression, across both short-term and long-term research (Holt et al., 2015; Kowalski et al., 2014; Moore et al., 2017).

What's particularly alarming is that being victimized through digital platforms has shown a stronger link to suicidal ideation and symptoms of depression than being bullied in person (Katsaras et al., 2018; van Geel et al., 2014). Research also suggests that gender plays a significant role, with girls often more vulnerable to the emotional consequences of cyberbullying than boys (Iranzo et al., 2019; Koyanagi et al., 2019; Kowalski et al., 2014).

One of the most distressing aspects of cyberbullying is its persistence—it can be relentless, invading a young person's life at all hours and offering little chance to escape. A meta-analysis by Landstedt and Persson (2014) further confirmed that online bullying has a stronger connection to suicidal thoughts than traditional peer harassment. In Saudi Arabia, for instance, a recent report revealed a sharp rise in cyberbullying among students in secondary schools and higher education—from 18% to nearly 27% (Al-Zahrani, 2015). Among younger children in primary schools and kindergartens, many were not even aware that cyberbullying is against the law. Although general awareness of the issue is improving, there are still significant misconceptions that need to be addressed (Allehyani, 2018).

Adolescents respond to cyberbullying in different ways, but emotions like anger, sadness, fear, anxiety, and depression are among the most common reactions (Ortega et al., 2012). Beyond emotional pain, cyberbullying can also affect students academically, leading to poor performance and increased school absenteeism (Chen et al., 2018).

In response to these growing concerns, this study aims to examine the link between cyberbullying and the emotional health and well-being of adolescents in secondary schools across Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Cyber bullying

Oxford English Dictionary (2015), cyber bullying refers to “the use of electronic communication to bully a person, typically by sending messages of an intimidating or threatening nature.” American National Crime Prevention Council (2018) defines it as "the method of using the Internet, cell phones or other devices to send or post text or images intended to hurt or embarrass another person.” Cyber bullying is an unfortunate social-product of recent communication technologies, particularly social interacting sites like Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, Twitter etc. Cyber bullying may involve posting rumours, threats, sexual remarks, personal or confidential information, or pejorative labels. With the increase of social media, comments, posts, photos and content shared by individuals can often be viewed by acquaintances in addition to strangers. The content shared by an individual online creates a kind of a permanent public record of their views, activities and behaviour. This public record of a person can be thought of like an online reputation. Cyber bullying can harm the online reputation of the person being bullied or the victim as well as the persons who participate in or incite bullying behaviour or the perpetrator. A few notable concerns of cyber bullying include:

It is Relentless: One of the most troubling aspects of cyberbullying is its constant presence. Unlike traditional bullying, which often ends once a person leaves a physical space, cyberbullying follows victims wherever they go. With digital devices and internet access available around the clock, harmful messages and harassment can appear at any time—day or night. This makes it incredibly difficult for victims to find relief or a safe space, as the bullying can feel inescapable and unending.

It Is Permanent: One of the most concerning aspects of cyberbullying is its lasting nature. Once something is shared online, it often becomes part of a person’s digital footprint—or digital shadow—which includes all the traceable activities, posts, and interactions an individual leaves behind on the internet or digital devices. If harmful content isn’t reported and removed promptly, it can remain public and accessible indefinitely, continuing to affect the victim long after the original incident.

It Is Difficult to Detect: Cyberbullying can be hard to recognize, especially for parents, teachers, or guardians, because it typically happens away from their view—on phones, computers, and other digital platforms. Unlike traditional bullying, there are no visible bruises or overheard confrontations. Additionally, many adolescents are reluctant to speak up about being cyberbullied, often keeping their pain hidden from the adults in their lives.

It Is Distinct from Traditional Bullying: While cyberbullying shares some similarities with face-to-face bullying, it also has key differences. A major distinction is that victims of cyberbullying often don’t know who is targeting them or why. In contrast, traditional bullying usually involves known individuals and clear, though unjustified, reasons. Cyber harassment also has the power to reach a much wider audience quickly—posts, messages, or images can be easily forwarded, reposted, or downloaded, making the harm more widespread and long-lasting.

As Willard (2016) explains in her book *Cyberbullying and Cyber Threats*, there are various forms of cyberbullying, each with its own damaging effects—further emphasizing the need for awareness, intervention, and digital responsibility.

Flaming: Flaming is a form of cyber bullying that refers to an argument or brief exchange between two or more people involving vulgar or rude language, threats and insults. It occurs in public Internet sites rather than private message exchanges.

Cyber harassment: Cyber harassment is a specific form of cyber bullying that involves repetitive offensive messages sent to a target (Kowalski, Limber & Agatston, 2012). Harassment usually takes place via private messages such as emails but can also be seen in public forums.

Denigration: Denigration is the spreading of information about another that is derogatory and untrue, including spreading gossip or rumours about someone in an effort to damage reputations and friendships (Willard, 2016). It refers to posting false information or rumours on webpages which are circulated through private communication channels. Included in this form of cyber bullying is the digital alteration

of photos, most commonly in a way that portrays someone in a sexualized or harmful manner (Kowalski, Limber & Agatston, 2012).

Impersonation: Impersonation is a method of cyber bullying in which the perpetrator poses as the victim and either sends or posts negative, cruel, or inappropriate information in an attempt to damage that person's reputation (Willard, 2016). Impersonation may also occur if the perpetrator poses as someone else entirely in an attempt to elicit information. This relates to another form of cyber bullying known as trickery that refers to talking someone into revealing secrets or embarrassing information and then sharing it online (Kowalski, Limber & Agatston, 2012). Sometimes trickery may lead to the outing, which refers to sharing of personal secrets or sensitive information without the victim's permission.

Exclusion or cyber- ostracism: Exclusion or cyber-ostracism refers to intentionally and cruelly excluding someone from an online group (Willard, 2016). It basically refers to "defriending" or blocking someone on Facebook, WhatsApp and similar social networking sites. Though not as harmful as other forms of cyber bullying, exclusion or even perceived exclusion has been related to lower self-esteem (Williams, Cheung & Choi, 2010).

Research has demonstrated a number of detrimental consequences of cyber bullying victimization. Victims usually suffer from low self-esteem, frustration, anger, depression as well as increased suicidal tendencies. In fact, cyber bullying is more harmful than traditional bullying because there is no escape from it. One of the most damaging effects is that the victim begins to avoid friends and social activities, excludes himself from the society which is the very intention of the bully. It is worth mentioning that cyber bullying is a form of psychological abuse whose victims are more than twice as likely to suffer from mental disorders as compared to traditional bullying. Moreover, research also illustrates that cyber bullying has adverse effects on adolescents than adults because they are still growing mentally and physically. They tend to hide their bullying experiences from adults or those who can help them to prevent the bullying from occurring and getting worse. Between 20% to 40% of adolescents are victims of cyber bullying worldwide, they are more vulnerable to the impact of cyber bullying through social media because adolescents are attracted to these platforms as a means of seeking validation from their peers. Cyber bullying has significant negative effect on students' overall well-being, specifically the emotional well-being, interpersonal functioning, social relationships, friendships, business relationships.

Concept of Emotional Well-being

Well-being refers to the overall quality of a person's life and their standard of living. It can be measured through both objective factors—such as family income, access to education, and physical health—and subjective experiences, including emotions, perceived quality of life, and personal life satisfaction (Casas, 2011). According to Kallay and Rus (2013), emotional well-being consists of two key dimensions: *hedonic* and *eudaimonic* well-being. Hedonic well-being focuses on happiness, pleasure, and life satisfaction—how good a person feels in their day-to-day life. On the other hand, eudaimonic well-being is more about meaning and purpose, emphasizing living in alignment with one's values and reaching one's full potential.

For adolescents, especially students, emotional well-being can be significantly disrupted by experiences of bullying—particularly cyberbullying. Being targeted online can interfere with their mental health and cognitive development in serious ways. The psychological effects are very real and can vary in intensity depending on the individual and the situation.

Many adolescents today also struggle with what's known as the "fear of missing out" (FOMO), which drives them to constantly check social media, trying to stay updated on every post or message from friends. This pressure can lead to anxiety, low self-esteem, and disrupted sleep, all of which can worsen into more severe issues like depression (Filucci, 2016).

Spencer (2018) found that the more a person is bullied, the more likely they are to experience problems in their relationships. Cyberbullying, in particular, can reduce concentration, increase feelings of depression, and damage social connections. Over time, it can also lower self-esteem and harm a young person's emotional well-being.

Adolescents today spend a significant portion of their time on social media, whether at school or at home. These platforms often serve as important spaces for social interaction, helping to shape their emotional and social development. However, misuse or overuse of these platforms—something common across many parts of the world—can have the opposite effect, hindering rather than supporting their growth.

In our digital age, adolescents connect with others and with the wider world primarily through technology. When used responsibly, social media can have a positive influence on emotional well-being. However, when misused, it can lead to emotional distress. It is within this context that this study aims to explore the importance of equipping adolescent students with the tools and awareness to maintain positive emotional well-being in their interactions online.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised to be tested in this study.

H1: There is no significant relationship between cyber bullying and emotional well-being among adolescents secondary school students.

H2: There is no significant difference between emotional well-being and cyber bullying based on gender among secondary school students.

METHOD

Research Design

This study adopted the correlation research design. This design is chosen because it allows the study of the relationship that exists between cyber bullying behaviour and emotional well-being among adolescents secondary school students. A correlation research design seeks to ascertain relationships between two or more variables.

Population

The population of the study comprised of 28, 634 senior secondary school two (SSS 2) students from the existing 159 public secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 450 SSS 2 students from the population of 28, 634 students were used for the study in accordance with sample size determination table. The multi-stage sampling procedures were used for this study. Multi-stage sampling procedure is a sampling technique that is used whenever different sampling methods are applied at several stages of the research study. Thus, in the first stage, simple random sampling was used to select two schools from each local government area, making a total of 18 schools. In the second stage, within the two schools selected for each of the local government areas, 50 students were selected from each of the nine local government areas, making a total of 450 students for the entire local government areas. In the third stage, the researchers used the purposive sampling technique to select respondents from each of the schools because it enables the researchers to have a good mix of students in respect to sex, age, class and home background characteristics.

Research Instruments

The questionnaire is the instrument used in the study. The instrument is divided into three sections A, B and C. Section A contains the student demographic variable. Section B contains items on Emotional well-being survey, which were adopted from the American college Health Foundation with the purpose of examining the overall well-being of college students, while Section C is Cyber bullying questionnaire (CBQ) by Prins, Bovin, Kimerling, Kaloupex, Marx, Kaiser & Schnurr (2015) which has items to which students have to respond on a continuum range of Strongly Agree (SA) 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1.

Reliability of the Instrument

In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, pilot studies were carried out. The data obtained from the pilot study were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient to determine the internal consistency of the various scales of the instruments. It yielded a coefficient of: Emotional well-being has $r=.69$, Cyber bullying has $r = .75$, after pilot testing.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers were assisted by two trained assistants to administer the questionnaire in schools, detailed explanation of the items on the questionnaire was explained to the students, and the completed questionnaire were administered and collected from the students on the spot using face- to-face method. This approach is aimed at minimizing the instrument’s mortality and attrition rate. Data from completed copies of questionnaire were collated for statistical data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher employed descriptive statistic of mean scores using 2.50 as benchmark to provide answers to the research questions. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Independent T-test Statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Hypotheses One: There is no significant relationship between emotional well-being and Cyber bullying of adolescent’s secondary school students.

Table 1: Showing the relationship between emotional well-being and Cyber Bullying behaviour.

Variables		Cyber Bullying	Emotional well-being
	Pearson Correlation	1	0.633**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Emotional well-being	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	430.56	123.33
	Covariance	12.45	4.61
	N	450	450
	Pearson Correlation	0.633**	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	
Cyber Bullying	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	123.33	113.57
	Covariance	4.61	3.67
	N	450	450

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From table 1, it can be observed that the Pearson correlation coefficient, *r*, is 0.633 and that it is significant at (*p* = 0.001). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between cyber bullying and emotional well-being of adolescent students. This indicates that cyber bullying negatively affects the emotional well-being and health of adolescent students.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant difference between emotional well-being and cyber bullying based on gender among secondary school students.

Table 2: Showing the mean, standard deviation and the Independent T-Test of gender, emotional well-being and cyber bullying.

Group Statistics							
Variables	Female	Male	N	t-cal	t-crit	df	Sig (2-tailed)
Mean	42.51	40.97	265	.444	1.97	498	.646
S.D	7.31	6.10	185	.357	1.97		.172
Emotional well-being	42.62	9.39	265	.			
Cyber Bullying	44.71	8.10	185				

Data in table 2 revealed the t-test was run to test the difference in the mean scores between cyber bullying and emotional well-being of adolescent students based on gender. The result indicate a significant

difference given that the mean scores for female = 42.51 and male = 40.97 and standard deviation scores of .731 and 6.10 for both female and male respectively with t- value = .444 and .357 for female and male respectively. This revealed that there is a significant difference between cyber bullying and emotional well-being of adolescent students based on gender. The mean scores obtained from table 2 further reveals that female students experience more of the psychological challenges associated with cyber bullying than their male counterparts.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first hypothesis tested revealed that there is a significant relationship between cyber bullying and emotional well-being and health of students. This is based on the result obtained (p value = $0.000 < 0.05$, $r = 0.633$) which shows that cyber bullying statistically correlates emotional well-being. This may be due to the fact that cyber bullying creates negative self image, anxiety problems, decreased self confidence, indulgence in risk taking behavior, substance abuse, feelings of helplessness, social isolation, withdrawal, and relationship loss. This finding is in line with Rao and Rao (2021) in their study were of the view that cyber bullying correlates with emotional health issues. This was supported by Englander (2021) who argued that it could lead to anxiety, psychological distress, and post-traumatic stress symptoms. Also, Nochaiwong et al. (2021) and Paat and Markham (2020) found out that cyber bullying is associated with emotional well-being of adolescents, Arguing in the same line, (Muhonen et al., 2017) revealed that victims of cyber bullying also shows lower engagement. These all go to show that cyber bullying is injurious to the emotional health of its victims especially adolescents.

The result of the second findings indicate a significant difference between cyber bullying and emotional well-being of adolescent students based on gender and the study notes that girls suffer more of the outcome of cyber bullying consequences than their counterparts in secondary schools. This finding is in line with the works of (Jenkins et al., 2018) in their study asserted that girls were more of the victims. Masselink et al. (2018) noted that girls experience more of the negative impact of cyber bullying on their emotional well-being. On the other hand, Martínez-Marín & Martínez, 2019 in their studies report boys as experiencing more negative emotional well being as a result of cyber bullying, Bastiaensens et al., 2014, reported that boys are more affected emotionally by the result of cyber bullying.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions are made based on the findings of the study

1. The study concludes that cyber bullying negatively influence students emotional well-being and health in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.
2. The study also revealed that female adolescents are more vulnerable and experience the effects of cyber bullying on their emotional health than their male counterparts in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There should be awareness created of the effect of cyber bullying on the emotional well-being and health of secondary school students.
2. The victims should be encouraged to report acts of cyber bullying which should be punished according to law.
3. Guidance counsellors should be encouraged to organize periodic therapeutic classes in secondary schools that can help to tackle victims of cyber bullying who are struggling with emotional health issues.
4. Female adolescents should be educated on the lookout for signs and triggers of cyber bullying, what to do in response and to report same to the appropriate authority so that they can tackle the occurrence between female and male students alike.

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